

MULTI-AXIAL MULTI-PLY CARBON FABRIC REINFORCED EPOXY COMPOSITES: MECHANICAL PROPERTIES AND INVESTIGATION OF INITIAL DAMAGE

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SUMMARY: The Resin Transfer Molding production of multi-axial multi-ply or non-crimp carbon fabric reinforced Epoxy composites was described. The mechanical properties of the composites such as tensile, in plane shear, out of plane shear properties were measured. The mechanical properties of different materials (quadriaxial, biaxial $\pm 45^\circ$, unidirectional laminates) were compared. Initial damage occurring in bi-directional laminates $0^\circ/90^\circ$ during tensile tests was investigated using acoustic emission, C-Scan and X-Ray technique. As expected, the quadriaxial laminates show a quasi-isotropic behavior while biaxial laminates show an an-isotropic behavior. The in plane shear properties of materials are strongly dependent on the amount of reinforcement in $+45^\circ$ and -45° relative to loading direction. By analyzing the acoustic emission data in combination with NDT techniques, the significantly initial damage developed in bi-directional laminated can be determined.

KEYWORDS: non-crimp fabrics, mechanical properties, NDT

INTRODUCTION

Recently, multi-axial multi-ply fabrics have attracted much attention of the composites industry [1,2,3]. Combination of unidirectional placement of fibres in plies with consolidation of the preform by stitching leads to a highly advantageous combination of material properties and processing. This results in the full use of fibre modulus and strength in a ready part and allows the use of Resin Transfer Moulding (RTM) for the production.

The considerable reduction in price of carbon fibres has opened a possibility for MMCF reinforced polymer composites to be used in more common applications such as marine or automotive (Palmer, 2001). To assess these possible applications, material properties as well as an investigation of damage development in the material are needed.

Therefore, experimental work to evaluate the mechanical properties and study on the damage development of multi-axial multi-ply carbon fabric reinforced epoxy composites was carried out at Departement Metaalkunde en Toegepaste Materiaalkunde (MTM) – Katholieke Universiteit Leuven (K.U.Leuven) (Lomov et al, 2001).

MATERIALS AND COMPOSITE PRODUCTION

The multi-axial multi-ply carbon reinforcement fabrics (Figure 1a,b) were provided by Saertex Wagener GmbH & Co. KG. Their parameters, as specified by the manufacturer, are shown in Table 1. The unidirectional fabric is stabilised by a UD layer of E-Glass 34 tex with areal density of 13 g/m² (Figure 1c).

Shell Epoxy Resin Epikote 828 LV together with Hardener Epikure DX 6514 were used as a matrix system. The mixing ratio between resin and hardener was 100/17.

Table 1: The specifications multi-axial multi-ply carbon fabrics.

Description	Quadriaxial carbon fabric	Bidiagonal carbon fabric	Unidirectional carbon fabric
Saertex Code	V91450-00630-01270 V91451-00630-01270	V91448-00320-01270 V91447-00320-01270	V91697-00170-01270
Orientation of plies, degrees	0;+45;90;-45 0;-45;90;+45	-45;+45 +45;-45	0
Material	12K Toray T700 50C, PES stitching	12K Toray T700 60E, PES stitching	Toray 24K T700 31E, PES stitching
Mass, g/sqm	644	300	165
Stitching pattern	Tricot-Warp binder	Tricot	Tricot-Warp binder

The RTM equipment at the Composite Laboratory of MTM Department-K.U. Leuven was used to make composite plates with a fibre volume fraction of 45% approximately. Before the placement of the fabrics, the cavity was warmed to 40°C. The fabrics were placed in the mold cavity in such a way as to get symmetry of stacking sequence about the plate mid-plane. After degassing, the resin was injected into the mold cavity with a pressure of 2 bars for 2 minutes. After that, the pressure was increased up to 4-5 bars until the cavity was filled. During injection, vacuum of -0.5 bar was applied in the cavity. After injection, the mold was heated to 70°C in 1 hour to cure the resin. Then the composite plate was demolded and post-cured in an air oven at 160°C in 1 hour.

Figure 1: The biaxial (a), quadriaxial (b), unidirectional fabric (c).

TESTING

1. Tensile test

Tensile tests were performed on quadriaxial laminate (Q), biaxial laminate (B) and unidirectional laminate (U) in machine direction (MD), bias direction (BD) and cross direction (CD) to determine Young modulus (E), Poisson ratio (ν), stress (σ^*) and strain (ϵ^*) at failure. The stress-strain curves were also obtained.

The ISO 527-4 “Test conditions for isotropic and an-isotropic fibre reinforced plastic composites” was followed to prepare the specimens and perform the tensile test. The Instron 4505 with hydraulic clamping was used as the testing equipment. The crosshead speed was set at 1 mm/min. A load cell of 100 kN was used to measure the force. To register the displacement in both length and width directions during the test, extensometers with a gauge length of 50 mm and 12.5 mm respectively were placed on the specimen. The specimen dimensions were 250 mm

Figure 2: The stress-strain curves of tensile test on quadriaxial laminate in different directions.

by 12.5 mm. During the tests, the temperature was conditioned to be 22 °C with a humidity of 40 %. During testing, the extensometer to measure the longitudinal displacement was attached tightly on the specimen by rubber rings. Normally, the composite specimens reinforced by carbon fibres might break violently when they fail. Therefore, to prevent the extensometer from being damaged, it should be removed at strain of ϵ_r before specimen failure. The part of the stress-strain curve for $\epsilon > \epsilon_r$ and strain at failure were back calculated from the strain measured from the cross head displacement.

1.1 Results of the tensile tests on quadriaxial laminates

The tensile properties of quadriaxial laminate in different directions are shown and compared in Table 2, Figure 2.

Table 2: Tensile properties of quadriaxial laminate in different directions.

	Modulus,GPa	Strength,MPa	Ult.strain (%)	Poisson Ratio	V_f (%)
MD	32.8±0.6	530.4±26.4	1.76±0.10	0.30±0.02	42.1±0.8
BD	38.3±1.7	575.3±45.3	1.62±0.14	0.38±0.07	44.5±1.2
CD	34.1±1.3	499.9±22.9	1.61±0.09	0.37±0.05	44.5±1.2

Note: ± means standard deviation in all the tables in the paper

The stress - strain curves of quadriaxial laminate in tensile tests in MD, BD and CD (Figure 2) show that the material behaves linearly until failure. The difference in stiffness and strength is approximately 14 %. It is due to the variation in fibre volume fraction and fibre orientation.

1.2 Results of the tensile tests on biaxial laminates

Table 3 and Figure 3 present the tensile properties of biaxial carbon fabric reinforced epoxy composites.

Unlike the quadriaxial laminates, the biaxial laminates are highly anisotropic materials in which the modulus and strength in bias direction are much higher than that in machine and cross direction (Figure 3). It is evident because in bias direction, the materials are reinforced by continuous fibres. It is also interesting to see that the properties in machine and cross direction are almost identical. The minor differences are due to the variation of fibre volume fraction).

Table 3: Tensile properties of biaxial laminate in different directions.

	Modulus,GPa	Strength,MPa	Ult.strain (%)	Poisson Ratio	V_f (%)
MD	9.9±0.4	177.4±3.9	8.7±0.3	0.83±0.04	39.4±1.8
BD	44.8±4.2	688.5±47.1	1.6±0.1	0.05±0.01	39.4±1.8
CD	9.5±0.4	159.7±1.7	9.4±0.9	0.82±0.04	36.9±1.1

Higher strain at failure in machine and cross direction is obtained because of the presence of fibres in +45° and -45° relative to these directions. In the specimens of the test in bias direction, there are fibres perpendicular to the loading direction. They prevent the specimens from contraction in the width direction, resulting in very low Poisson ratio.

Figure 3: The stress-strain curves of tensile tests on biaxial laminate in different directions.

1.3 Results of the tensile tests on unidirectional laminates

The results of tensile tests on unidirectional laminates, as well as stress-strain curves are shown on Table 4, Figure 4.

Table 4: Tensile properties of unidirectional laminate in different directions.

	Modulus,GPa	Strength,MPa	Ult.strain (%)	Poisson Ratio	V_f (%)
MD	94.3±8.2	1232.9±85.4	1.49±0.09	0.32±0.04	42.8±0.8
BD	8.6±0.3	96.1±2.8	1.81±0.11	0.41±0.02	42.8±0.8
CD	7.8±0.3	59.6±1.4	0.84±0.06	0.03±0.00	45.9±0.8

The tensile modulus of 94.3 GPa measured in the test on unidirectional laminate in machine direction is close to the result calculated from the Rule of Mixture:

$$E_1 = E_f * V_f + E_m * (1 - V_f) = 103.2 \text{ GPa}$$

where $E_f = 238 \text{ GPa}$ (provided by Saertex Wagener GmbH & Co. KG), $E_m = 2.73 \text{ GPa}$ (tested at MTM- KU Leuven), $V_f = 0.43$.

The presence of fibres in the 45° direction relative to the loading direction results in higher strength and modulus in bias direction compared with those in cross direction. The Poisson ratio of the material tested in cross direction is quite low. It is again because of the presence of the fibres in the 90° direction relative to the loading direction, which prevents the contraction of the material in this direction. The non-linear behaviour of the material tested in machine direction for $\sigma > 1000$ MPa (Figure 4) can be attributed to a certain deformation of the testing rig or a minor slippage or deformation in the grips. Anyway, the measured ultimate strain of 1.49 % is close to its value for carbon fibres of 1.5 %.

Figure 4: The stress-strain curves of tensile tests on unidirectional laminate in different directions.

Thus the observed non-linearity can represent the real material behaviour and the strain of 1.2 % and 1.49 % can be considered as the lower and upper bound of strain at failure respectively.

The relatively large scatter in strength ($\pm 8\%$ approximately) between the tests may be due to the variation of the fibre orientation or / and fibre volume fraction.

1.4 Short beam shear test

To determine the interlaminar shear strength of the composites in machine direction, the short beam shear tests were performed following ISO 14130 “Fibre reinforced plastic composites – Determination of apparent interlaminar shear strength by short beam method”. The Instron 4467 was used as testing machine. The cross-head speed was 1 mm/min. A load cell of 30 kN was used to measure the load. The diameter of the loading and supporting members were 10 mm and 5 mm respectively. The span used was 16 mm. The specimens dimensions were 30 mm by 15 mm and 3.4 mm thick. During the tests, the temperature was conditioned to be 22 °C with a humidity of 40 %.

Table 5: The interlaminar shear strength of composites in machine direction.

Material	Interlaminar shear strength (MPa)	Ultimate deflection (mm)	$V_f(\%)$
Quadriaxial	36.2±1.1	0.5±0.04	43.8±0.8
Biaxial	38.4±1.2	1.0±0.10	39.4±1.8
Unidirectional	73.7±1.8	0.7±0.03	42.8±0.8

The interlaminar shear strength τ^u of quadriaxial, biaxial and unidirectional fabric reinforced epoxy composites are presented on Table 5. The interlaminar shear strength is obtained when the beam fails in the interlaminar shear mode by cracking along a horizontal plane between the lamina [4]. In quadriaxial and biaxial laminates, there are fibres in +45° and -45° relative to the machine direction. They may initiate vertical cracks easily hence resulting in lower interlaminar shear strength compared with that of unidirectional laminates. The τ^u data are derived from the maximum load, which is assumed to coincide with the first shear crack. However, some non-linearity of the stress-strain curve

(starting at approximately 60% of maximum load) would indicate early compressive or shear damage. The τ^u hence can be considered as an upper bound.

1.5 Iosipescu test

ASTM D 5379 / D 5379M – 93 “Standard test method for shear properties of composite materials by the V-notched beam method” was used to prepare the specimens and perform the test to measure in plane shear properties of the materials: shear modulus (G), shear strength (τ^u). The Instron 1196 and V-notched beam test fixture were used in the tests. Strain gauges with an active gauge length of 3 mm were used to measure shear strain. The cross-head speed was set at 1 mm/min. A load cell of 20 kN was used. According to the standard, the quadriaxial and unidirectional laminates were tested in machine direction while the biaxial laminate was tested in bias direction. The specimen dimensions were 76 mm by 19 mm and 3.4 mm thick. Three mm thick end tabs were used to strengthen and stabilise the specimens. They also help to prevent the specimens from compression failure. During the tests, the temperature was conditioned to be 22 °C with a humidity of 40 %.

Table 6 shows the in plane shear properties of quadriaxial, biaxial and unidirectional laminates. The quadriaxial laminate has the highest shear strength and modulus. It is evident because the material was reinforced by +45° and –45° layers, which significantly enhance the shear properties.

Table 6: The in plane shear properties of quadriaxial, biaxial and unidirectional laminates.

Material	Shear Modulus (GPa)	Shear strength (MPa)	V_f (%)
Quadriaxial (MD)	11.3±0.8	222.0±13.9	42.1±0.8
Biaxial (BD)	3.3±0.3	61.5±4.8	39.4±1.8
Unidirectional (MD)	2.4±0.4	71.3±0.3	42.8±0.8

The shear strength of the biaxial laminate of 62 MPa is considered as the lower bound because it coincides with the first crack occurring during testing. It is quite difficult to determine the “real” shear strength of this material due to the presence of fibres perpendicular to the loading direction. They bridge the material on both sides of the notch and continue to support the specimen. After initiation of the first crack, if the test is going on stress increases until the specimen hits the bottom of the fixture.

INITIAL DAMAGE IN BI-DIRECTIONAL LAMINATES (0°/90°)

1. Test set up

To investigate the initial damage occurring in bi-directional laminate (0°/90°), the acoustic emission system Wave Explorer was employed in tensile tests. The damages in tested specimens were then detected by S-can and X-Ray (Philips HOMX 161) equipment at MTM Department-K.U. Leuven.

Fig. 5 Tensile specimen with Acoustic Emission sensors

Figure 5 shows the set up of specimens for the test. Two acoustic emission sensors were attached 30 mm away from the extensometer gauge length. Pencil tests were performed outside the area between two sensors to determine the velocity of sound in the material by using the difference in arrival time to two sensors of the waves created by the pencil break and the distance between them. With the velocity of the sound, source of the signals can be localised hence the signals created outside the sensors were filtered out. This secures that the noise from the grips and the machine was eliminated.

2. Results and discussion

Fig.6 Tensile tests on bi-directional laminate in machine direction

- Transition point on the curve event number vs strain (at 0.3% in this case)
- Stiffness slightly increases

Figure 6 presents the information obtained from the test including stiffness, total AE counts, stress and event energy versus strain. From the beginning of the tensile test on bi-directional laminates in machine direction, AE signals were already collected by the AE system. It indicated that micro damages occurred from the start of the test. However, these micro-damages did not reduce tensile modulus of specimens, instead it slightly increased.

Fig.7 Cumulative energy of AE signals in tensile test on bi-directional laminate in machine direction.

- Thin line: cumulative energy of AE signals of individual test
- Thick line: average cumulative energy of AE signals of 5 tests

In the range of strain between 0.2 % and 0.4 % (Fig. 6), more specifically at the strain close to 0.3 %, the signals were found with relatively high energy (varying from 27 to 311 energy unit) compared to the energy of the signal occurred before (from 0 % to 0.2 %). Moreover, strain of 0.3 % is also the transition point at which the number of events increases quickly.

Figure 7 shows the cumulative energy of AE signals from tensile test on bi-directional in machine direction. The value of the cumulative energy at a certain strain ε was computed as a sum of energy of all the AE events between $(\varepsilon-\Delta\varepsilon, \varepsilon+\Delta\varepsilon)$ with $\Delta\varepsilon = 0.025$ %. In average, it was very low at the beginning then started to increase at the strain of 0.2 % approximately up to 0.4 %. From the strain of 0.4 %, the energy formed a plateau until the end of the test.

From the above observation and the outcomes of previous study [8], it is expected that initial damage may occur at a strain around $\varepsilon_1 = 0.2\%$ at which the number of AE signal sharply increases. Therefore, to inspect the initial damage and damage development, tensile tests were performed on bidirectional laminate in machine direction at 3 different strain levels 0.2%, 0.8% and 1.3%. Damages in tested specimens were then detected by using C-Scan and X-Ray technique.

Fig. 8 Damage evolution in bidirectional laminate under tensile loading in machine direction. Ultrasonic images(I.a, I.b, I.c) and X-Ray images (II.a, II.b, II.c, II.d).

Figure 8 presents the results of the study with the master curve, C-scan images I.a, I.b, I.c and X-ray images II.a, II.b, II.c. It is clearly seen that the initially transverse crack was observed at $\epsilon_1 = 0.2\%$ by X-Ray from the edge of specimen (Fig. II.d). Then the micro damages, which were heard and observed, in tested specimens increased as the applied strain increased. The images revealed that at low strain, transverse matrix cracks were dominant. At higher strain when the transverse matrix cracks were saturated, cracks along fibres started at lower strain increase.

Therefore, it can be concluded that initial damage occurred at the strain approximately 0.2% - 0.3% and stress of 130 MPa (20 % of tensile strength). Indeed, more work should be done to understand better damage development in this material and to see if stitching affects the material behaviour.

As mentioned before, in tensile test on bi-directional laminates in machine direction, the stiffness of the material slightly increased instead of decreasing. It is evident because in this direction bi-directional laminates are fibre-dominated materials in which the contribution of matrix to the material stiffness is minor. The initial damage is mainly matrix cracks and hence did not reduce the material stiffness a lot. The stiffness reduction due to matrix cracks was compensated by stiffness increase due to the increase of carbon stiffness under stretching.

CONCLUSION

The mechanical properties of multi-axial multi-ply carbon fabric reinforced epoxy composites were determined. The quadriaxial laminates show a quasi-isotropic behaviour, while the biaxial and unidirectional laminates clearly present an an-isotropic one. The properties of the fibres are almost translated into the unidirectional laminates. It was confirmed again that the in plane shear properties are strongly dependent on the amount of $+45^\circ$ and -45° reinforcements. Unidirectional laminates have highest interlaminar shear strength.

Based on NTD techniques including acoustic emission, S-Scan, X-Ray, the initially transverse matrix crack was found at the strain close to $\varepsilon_1 = 0.2\%$, at which the AE event counts rapidly rose. As applied strain increased, matrix cracks increased. The material stiffness, however, did not decrease because the contribution of matrix for stiffness of this fibre-dominated material was not significant.

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